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The Impact of the Telegram Application on Enhancing Students' English Writing Skills in Higher Institutions in Sokoto, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

This study investigated the impact of the Telegram application on enhancing students' learning of English writing at Shehu Shagari College of Education and Sokoto State University, Sokoto, Nigeria. A purposive sample was used, consisting of 200-level students from the English Language Departments of SSCO (affiliated with Usmanu Danfodiyo University) and SSU. An intact classroom setting was employed to achieve the objectives of the study, and a quasi-experimental research design was adopted. Control and experimental groups were established to examine the effect of using Telegram in enhancing students' writing skills. The experimental group was taught essay writing using Telegram, while the control group received traditional instruction. The researcher developed Telegram-based sessions featuring activities related to essay writing, incorporating multimedia such as pictures, videos, and short essays to improve content, organization, expression, and mechanical accuracy. To assess the effectiveness of the intervention, the researcher developed a pre- and post-writing test, evaluated using a writing rubric. Data were analyzed statistically using means, standard deviations, and an independent samples t-test to compare the performance of both groups. The reliability of the instrument was measured using Guttman split-half method. The intervention lasted four weeks, during which the experimental group received writing instruction through Telegram, including feedback, corrections, and peer suggestions. The findings revealed a statistically significant improvement in the writing performance of the experimental group, indicating that Telegram positively impacted ESL students' essay writing skills.

Keywords: Telegram application, ESL writing skills, Quasi-experimental design, Social media in education, Essay writing improvement

INTRODUCTION

Telegram application is a cloud based instant messaging service developed by Telegram Messenger LLP, a privately held company register in London, United Kingdom, founded by the Russian entrepreneur Pavel Durov and brother Nikolai (Thomas & Bhat, 2022). Telegram client apps are available for android, Ios, Windows phone, Windows, macOS and Linux. With Telegram, you can send messages, photos, videos and files of any type (doc, zip, mp3, etc), as well as create groups for up to 100,000 people or channels for broadcasting to unlimited audiences(Thomas & Bhat, 2022).

Through telegram app a teacher can blended learning and flipped classroom, use before class, during the class and after the class and also alternative platform for forum. Writing is one of the language skills which second language learners are struggling with, the areas of writing that many second language learners perceive difficult range from composing processes (planning and revising) to written text features (fluency, accuracy and structure) Silvia (2000). Teachers are the gatekeepers of technology integration in

the classroom; they play an important role in its success or failure in education (Tondeur et al., 2019). There is no doubt that learning takes place when learners' tendencies and habits are taken into account and made use of. Therefore, teachers should be creative in turning technological addiction by youngsters into something beneficial for their education especially in learning a second language.

Concept of Telegram

Telegram is a non-profit cloud-based instant messaging service. Telegram client apps exist for Android, iOS, Windows Phone, Windows NT, macOS and Linux. [2] Users can send messages and exchange photos, videos, stickers, audio and files of any type.

Telegram was founded by the Russian entrepreneur Pavel Durov. Its client-side code is open-source software but the source code for recent versions is not always immediately published, whereas its server-side code is closed-source and proprietary. The service also provides APIs to independent developers.

Telegram's security model has received notable criticism by cryptography experts. They have argued that it is undermined by its use of a custom-designed encryption protocol that has not been proven reliable and secure, by storing all messages on their servers by default and by not enabling end-to-end encryption for messages by default. Pavel Durov has argued that this is because it helps to avoid third-party unsecure backups and to allow users to access messages and files from any device. Messages in Telegram are server-client encrypted by default, and the service provides end-to-end encryption for voice calls and optional end-to-end encrypted "secret" chats. Scott & nick (2022).

Telegram offers several features that support educational use, particularly in teaching writing. A Telegram account provides access to a range of tools, including cloud-based messages, which allow users to access conversations and shared materials from any device. Telegram channels enable educators to broadcast messages, resources, and assignments to large groups of students efficiently. Telegram bots can automate responses, deliver quizzes, and provide instant feedback, enhancing engagement and interaction. Additionally, Telegram stickers can be used creatively to support vocabulary and expression, while Telegram drafts allow users to save unfinished messages, which can be helpful for writing practice. Voice calls facilitate real-time communication and feedback between teachers and students. In terms of pedagogical application, learning theories such as behaviorism can be applied through Telegram by reinforcing correct writing behavior with immediate feedback and rewards, making it a valuable tool in the field of teaching writing. Skinner (1948) emphasized that any behavior is the result of stimulus-response- reinforcement and telegram is full of stimulus-response activities and it is also full of reinforcement. Using telegram is a behavior and learning how to write effectively through telegram is another behavior which could be enjoyably applied and determined by the environment (Watson, 1920).

Concept of Essay Writing

The idea in an essay is arranged and expressed in an orderly manner. According to Egudu (1990): an introductory paragraph, which introduces the essay and states the main point in a thesis statement, the body which supports (shows, explains or proves) main point. It consists of support paragraphs.

These support paragraphs containing facts and details supporting the main point. A concluding paragraph reminds readers of the main point. It may also summarize the support paragraphs or make an observation in a concluding sentence. The essay is composed about a topic. The writer breaks this topic into its different parts or sections and writes a short piece on each of these parts or sections. The short pieces written on the parts or sections make up the body of the essay or composition. The short pieces written about the different parts or sections of the topic are called paragraphs. According to Azikiwe (2007), the language of an essay should be as simple and clear as possible because one will not be called back to explain what he/she has written. Another important thing in an essay is the topic in question. The language and expressions one employs in writing are expected to be those that suit the topic under discussion. In fact, every type of speech made to our listeners can be represented in essay writing. Some speeches involve telling stories, others entail describing something while some may be in form of debate and so on. In that way, essay is classified into four main types; narrative essay, descriptive essay, expository essay and argumentative essay. There are various features of writing assessed in this study

which can be enhancing with the use of telegram. Various features assessed are: content and mechanical accuracy. Each of this is explicated.

The roles of teachers need to change from being arbiters of knowledge but facilitators of knowledge specifically by helping students to improve their writing skills Wells (2002). It is reasonable to assert that teachers can also interact with the learners even at home with the use of telegram Aladsani (2021). In addition, students would be able to provide the teachers with a constant feedback; this is consequently helpful to teachers to activate their willingness to discharge their duties and responsibilities.

According to Conde et al. (2021) installed applications such as telegram only motivate the Net-generation learners to use relevant learning materials, but also allow learners to experience the authentic usage of a language in communication. The use of technology especially the use of telegram is fast growing in various tertiary institutions within and outside Nigeria, because telegram is unique in its own way because it has certain features that place it above competitors prominent among the features are:

Telegram has the ability to share file type up to 1.5 GB compare to WhatsApp, Telegram supports multi device sessions, so you start chatting on one device and continue it on another, All the messages too are synced between deices in real time, so it is quick and efficient, Telegram include super group which can hold up to 1000 members along with cool public as well as private channels (Markudova, 2023). Telegram Bots: Telegram bots are basically telegram account created to do certain task, Telegram allows you to edit messages and mention people, and also is based on MTproto mobile protocol and brings end to end encryption with secret chats (Thomas & Bhat, 2022).

Statement of the problem

The rate of using social media among students in various higher institutions in Sokoto State cannot be over-exaggerated in the recent time. Today, smart-phones plus social networks are very popular among youngsters to the extent that it has metamorphosed into an addiction for them. Therefore, teachers should be creative in turning technological addiction by youngsters into something beneficial for their education especially in learning a second language. Second language learning is one of the demanding activities for learners; so, adding color and variety to these activities may set the stage to improve the writing skills of second language learners. For instance, producing errors-free paragraphs and essays even though they have been taught the main techniques of writing step by step is more worrisome.

More concretely, in the learning process, writing becomes a problem for two hundred level students of Shehu Shagari College of Education affiliated Usman Dan Fodio university Sokoto students and Sokoto state university as observed by the researcher. There are some problems that relate to the English writing process. For instance, the students' understanding of the aspects of writing is poor and consequently contributes to their lack of competency in writing, poor use of grammar, mechanical accuracy, content, organization and expression are of concern. They have difficulties in taking words to context when developing sentences, so majority of the student cannot compose a good paragraph. This study examined impact of telegram application on ESL learners' writing skills.

Specifically, the following are the objectives of the study:

1. To find the impact of telegram application on content development in essay writing between student taught using telegram app and those taught using lecture method.
2. To find out the impact of telegram application on mechanical accuracy in essay writing between student taught using telegram app and those taught using lecture method.

Research Questions

The following research questions would guide this study:

What are the impacts of telegram application on content development in essay writing between student taught using telegram app and those taught using lecture method?

What are the impacts of telegram application on mechanical accuracy in essay writing between student taught using telegram app and those taught using lecture method?

Null Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses will be tested at 0.05 significant:

H₀₁: There is no significant difference between the mean scores of students taught using telegram application to improve content development in essay writing and those taught using lecture method

H₀₂: There is no significant difference between the mean scores of students taught using telegram application to improve mechanical accuracy in essay writing and those taught using lecture method. The study is intended to improve students' writing skills through the use of telegram with particular reference to second year students of Shehu Shagari College of Education affiliated Usmanu Danfodiyo University and Sokoto state university.

METHODOLOGY

Quasi-experimental design was adopted as a design for this study. Two intact classes were used for the pretest and posttest. The sample of the study was group into two: the control and the experimental group respectively. Quasi experimental design is chosen because the study requires non-randomization of samples. The experimental group was taught using a platform on telegram application while the control was taught using lecture method.

The population of this research consisted of second year students of the nine tertiary institutions across in Sokoto state. There are 10,961 second year students across the tertiary institutions under the study. (Research and statistics department of Ministry of Higher Education in Sokoto State and admission officers of the tertiary institution). Purposive sampling technique was used to select the sample. Purposive sampling technique is one of the non-probability sampling techniques based on the judgment of the researcher. Also stratified sampling was used. With stratified sampling, the research divides the population into separate groups, called strata. Then, a probability sample is drawn. The researcher recommended this type of sampling because is suitable for this kind of research. The sample of this study was drawn from the population of all second-year undergraduate students from English department of Shehu Shagari College of Education Sokoto affiliated Usman Danfodio University and Sokoto state university Sokoto because their syllabus contains English composition. Intact classroom was used. SSCOE students served as the experimental group because the researcher has full control of the class being a lecturer in the college while the SSU students served as the control group. The summary of the population can be seen below:

Table 1: The table shows the target population and sample under the study.

School	Group	Number of student
Sokoto State University	Control	31
S.S.C.O.E Sokoto in Affiliation with UDUS	Experimental	48

The instrument that was used in carrying out this study is an Essay Writing Skill Test which was administered before and after the experiment. The EWST was constructed by the researcher to find out the extent to which student understand essay writing taught in the second-year syllabus. The factors that were considered when adopting the test item were based on the following: Content which include, relevance, buttress topic sentences, looking at points from all angle and sequencing, and mechanical accuracy; punctuation marks, correct spellings, good tenses and syntax.

The (EWST) consists of one questions for the student to answer and write about three or four paragraphs. The test items of the EWST covered the entire topic taught during the research. The essay was marked using WAEC and NECO marking scheme The EWST item was used in two different occasions; A-first, as pre –test, to determine the strength and equivalence of the sample at the beginning of the study. B-second, as post –test, to assess the performance of the student after the treatment

The prepared essay writing test to measure the impact of telegram on enhancing student writing skills was administered as pre-test and a post test in control group and experimental group. The control group was taught using lecture method and the experiment group was taught using a plat form on telegram application where the Students received intensive training of correcting each other's' mistakes and giving some suggestions to improve writing through a group on Telegram. The researcher's job was to administer the whole work including corrections, commenting and giving suggestions for presenting ideas in a better way.

Week 1-The students are exposed essay writing, types of essay writing, features of a good essay and examples of short essay writing.

Week 2- Pictures, videos, were posted to the platform. The researcher asked the student to look and watch the pictures and videos carefully and use them in generating more content in writing their essay. By looking at the picture the students will look for keywords like describe, discuss, analyze and compare. The students are asked to write short essay on descriptive essay

Week 3- The students are exposed to writing expository essay putting more emphasis in using past tense, past continuous tense, simple present tense. By the end of the third week the student were able to writing a very good essay.

Week 4-The students were given some unpunctuated passages to put punctuation on them.

The control groups were taught using lecture method with composition through pictures text book.

The instruments were validated by the supervisors and two other senior lecturers from Shehu Shagari College of Education Sokoto. For an item to satisfy the requirement of content validity, it must enjoy the unanimous agreement of all panel members in respect of each purpose.

To determine the reliability of the instrument, a test re-test method was employed. Guttman Split Half Coefficient was used to determine the reliability index. Isaac & Michael (1995) recommended 10 to 30 subjects for pilot testing. 20 students from two hundred levels from Usmanu Danfodio University were split into two and carried out the test, the same test was given to them but the numbers of questions were twisted. The researcher correlates the two performances and the coefficient of 0.973 was obtained. The Essay Writing Skill Test (EWST) test was administered to the sample first, as pre-test by the researcher. After four weeks period of instruction by the researcher; the EWST was administered to the two groups in the form of an examination as a post-test. Both groups wrote on paper to avoid plagiarism by those taught using telegram application. The researcher used the quantitative data analysis methods. The Data analysis made utilizing (SPSS, 25.0). The researcher utilized the following statistical methods:

FINDINGS

Answering Research Questions

In answering the research questions, the Essay Writing Skills Test (EWST) scores for both groups were analyzed using descriptive statistics (Mean and Standard deviation) because they provide summary used to describe the basic features of the data collected.

Research Question 1: *What are the impacts of telegram application on essay writing content learning?*

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics of Performance on essay Writing Content learning between Students Taught Using Telegram Application and those taught Using Conventional Lecture Method

Groups	N	Mean	Mean Difference	Std. Deviation
Telegram Application	48	7.56	4.66	1.35
Conventional Method	31	2.90		1.42

Source: field work 2022

Table 2 above presents the data of students' performance on essay writing content learning between those taught using telegram application and those taught using Conventional lecture method. Results shows that those taught using telegram application performed better with mean performance of 7.56 over those taught using Conventional lecture method with mean performance of 2.90. Therefore, there is difference of 4.66 in the mean performance between those taught using telegram application and those taught using Conventional lecture method but in favor of those taught using telegram.

Research Question 2: *What are the effects of telegram application on mechanical accuracy in essay writing of two hundred level students?*

Table 3: Descriptive Statistics of Performance on mechanical accuracy in essay writing between Students Taught Using Telegram Application and Those Taught Using Conventional Lecture Method

Groups	N	Mean	Mean Difference	Std. Deviation
Telegram Application	48	3.96	1.60	0.79
Conventional Method	31	2.36		1.08

Source: field work 2022

Table 2 above presents the data of students' performance on mechanical accuracy in essay writing between those taught using telegram application and those taught using Conventional lecture method. Results shows that those taught using telegram application performed better with mean performance of 3.96 over those taught using Conventional lecture method with mean performance of 2.36. Therefore, there is difference of 1.60 in the mean performance between those taught using telegram application and those taught using Conventional lecture method but in favor of those taught using telegram application.

Testing of Null Hypotheses

In testing the formulated null hypotheses, T-test statistics are used, because it is the most suitable for testing significance difference between the groups.

Null Hypothesis 1 (H_{01}): There is no significant difference between the mean scores of students taught using telegram application to improve essay writing content and those taught using conventional lecture method.

Table 4: T-Test Analysis of Mean Performance between Students Taught Using Telegram Application to Improve Essay Writing Content and those taught using Conventional Lecture Method

Groups	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	dF	t-value	p-value	Decision
Telegram Application	48	7.56	1.35	77	14.66	0.000	Rejected
Conventional Method	31	2.90	0.42				

Source: field work 2022

$\alpha = 0.05$ level of significance

Table 4.1 above shows the calculated p-value of 0.000 which is less than 0.05 level of significant at DF is 77. This indicated that, there is significant difference between the mean scores of students taught using telegram application to improve essay writing content and those taught using conventional lecture method but in favors of those taught using telegram application. It follows that the null hypothesis was rejected.

Null Hypothesis 4 (H_{04}): There is no significant difference between the mean scores of students taught using telegram application to improve essay writing mechanical accuracy and those taught using conventional lecture method.

Table 4. T-Test Analysis of Mean Performance between Students taught using Telegram Application to Improve Essay Writing Mechanical Accuracy and those taught using Conventional Lecture Method

Groups	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	DF	t-value	p-value	Decision
Telegram Application	48	3.96	0.79	77	7.57	0.000	Rejected
Conventional Method	31	2.36	1.08				

Source: field work 2022

$\alpha = 0.05$ level of significance

Table 4.8 above shows the calculated p-value of 0.000 which is less than 0.05 level of significant at Df is 77. This indicated that there is significant difference between the mean scores of students taught using

telegram application to improve essay writing mechanical accuracy and those taught using conventional lecture method but in favor of those taught using telegram application. It follows that the null hypothesis was rejected.

Summary of findings

The research questions in the current study set out to determine if the use of telegram will develop the students' writing skills. Based on the findings of this study, the results showed that using telegram has a significant effect on the students' levels of essay writing in favor of the experimental group who were taught telegram in line with findings of Alakrash (2020) who examined the effectiveness of employing Telegram application in teaching vocabulary: A quasi experimental study. This means that telegram is considered effective in improving students' essay writing skills since it leads to activate students' creative and critical thinking to write about various topics in an academic method.

The students' essay writing competence was enhanced when they were given opportunities to use telegram for discussions. A larger number of students wrote better using more meaningful contents within a well-organized essay in the post-test. More importantly, the students also had positive attitudes toward this social networking site. In their opinion, telegram was an alternative and up-to-date learning tool which was easily accessible. It provided convenience and more choices for students to study the English language, thus developing their writing competence. They overcame their shyness and dared to ask people questions on telegram. They could leave messages for the teacher or other telegram users. They could practice their English writing before they took the writing test. Additionally, these findings are congruent with previous studies showing that telegram is an effective tool for language teaching and learning.

The current study revealed that the paired group results in the posttest after implementing telegram showed an increase in their performance in the main skills of essay writing, namely (content, expression, organization and mechanical accuracy) supported by the findings of Aghajani and Adloo (2018) who investigated the Effect of Online Cooperative Learning on Students' Writing Skills and Attitudes through Telegram Application. Furthermore, the results of the posttest showed that 100% of the students succeeded after using the telegram and no one failed, whereas 90% of the students failed in the pre-test before conducting the telegram. These results emphasize the significant impact of telegram on enhancing the students' writing skills especially in writing telegram.

CONCLUSION

This study examined the impact of using telegram on improving student Writing Skills among SSCOE students and SSU students. The results of the study however, shed some light on issues concerning using new, modern and enthusiastic social networking websites especially telegram in the academic field of teaching the writing skills. In general, the results show that there were effective and obvious effects in using telegram on improving the students' writing skills especially the skills of (content and mechanical accuracy)

Implication of the Study

The result from the findings indicates the performance of students in the experimental group performed better than their counterparts in the control group. This shows that telegram has an impact on the performance of student English writing. This research work had implication on the students likewise the teachers. There is need for the teachers to acquire knowledge on the use of technology in education especially in the use of social media platform, i.e. telegram in teaching student writing.

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